

THE MODERATING EFFECT OF SCHOOL CULTURE ON THE RELATIONSHIP OF INDIGENOUS PEOPLES LANGUAGE ATTITUDE AND USAGE

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 32

Issue 10

Pages: 1225-1256

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3135

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14967830

Manuscript Accepted: 02-10-2025

The Moderating Effect of School Culture on the Relationship of Indigenous Peoples Language Attitude and Usage

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Abstract

School culture is found to be a significant factor that can moderate the relationship between indigenous peoples' language attitudes and the level of indigenous language usage among college students. Using the mean scores, results revealed that Indigenous students generally hold a favorable attitude towards their indigenous language. They have also shown moderate use of their indigenous language, as indicated by their regular use of the language and sense of commitment to its preservation. Moreover, the school, where they are enrolled, has a culture that supports intentions and behaviors in the use of the indigenous language by the students. Using moderated regression analysis, the causal relationship between students' attitude toward the indigenous language and their usage of the language was found to be significant at low and average levels of school culture (p -values =0.004 and 0.001, respectively) but became insignificant at high level of school culture (p -value=0.397). These findings implied that the school's support of the use of indigenous language, up to an average level, can strengthen the causal relationship between students' attitude toward their indigenous language and their usage of the language. However, at a high level of support, school culture can no longer moderate the causal relationship between the two variables. This study emphasizes the importance of the school calibrating its support of intentions and behaviors of students towards their indigenous language if it wants to affect the strength of the relationship between the two variables.

Keywords: *language, indigenous language attitude, indigenous language usage, multiple linear regression, Philippines*

Introduction

An attitude towards indigenous language can influence its use, and this causal relationship is moderated by school culture. However, the problem arises when school environments fail to support and encourage the use of indigenous languages, leading to the risk of these languages being forgotten and ultimately lost.

Indigenous languages are crucial to the identity of indigenous peoples. If they cannot freely use their languages, these languages may die, leading to the ultimate loss of their culture and identity. According to the Summer Institute of Linguistics (SIL), the Philippines boasts 183 living languages, with nearly ninety-six per cent being indigenous. However, eleven of these languages are classified as "dying," and 28 are considered "in trouble." Sadly, two Aeta languages—Dicamay Agta and Villa Viciosa Agta—have already become extinct (Reysio-Cruz, 2019). Indigenous languages decline for several reasons: younger generations often adopt the dominant national language instead of their ancestral one, communities may feel compelled to integrate into mainstream culture due to legal or cultural pressures, and schools predominantly teach the dominant language, neglecting Indigenous languages in their educational curriculum (Andrews, 2023).

Around the globe, some boarding schools were perceived as places where indigenous cultures were systematically suppressed and erased—a phenomenon sometimes termed "culturecide" in the United States. Students often faced punishment for speaking their indigenous languages, leading to profound effects of forced assimilation on Native

American education (Native Hope, 2023). Similarly, in Mexico, students were subjected to physical punishment for speaking indigenous languages at school (Shay, 2024). Furthermore, indigenous individuals in Australia often experience a lack of representation and influence in educational settings, as revealed by the study of Shay (2024). This absence of voice in schools hampers their ability to preserve and express their cultural identity, contributing significantly to their mental health struggles and overall well-being. Recognizing the importance of indigenous languages in education, some countries like Aotearoa New Zealand, Australia, and Canada have implemented initiatives to support the learning of indigenous languages, which has been shown to positively impact students' experiences and outcomes in education (Angelo, et al. 2022).

In Asia, one may hear the same narrative about the flexibility or inflexibility of attitudes towards indigenous languages and their use in a school setting. In multilingual Asian countries, the use of dominant languages like Mandarin, Hindi, and Bahasa in schools has overshadowed minority languages, moderating students' casting an unfavorable eye and eventual abandonment of their Indigenous languages (Roche et al., 2022). A study by Sukanto (2021) revealed that the use of English as the medium of instruction in an international school can be particularly critical for how Indonesian students perceive their home language as it relates to its use in their daily conversations. Sudoh and Darr (2022) reported that Asian countries often have national language policies favoring a single official language in education, often excluding Indigenous mother tongues. This can affect students in Southeast Asia who speak an indigenous language at home and their opportunity to use it in school (Maliwat, 2021). The lack of indigenous language instruction in schools can contribute to language shift, as children are unable to develop proficiency in their mother tongue and may come to see it as less valuable

(Alieto, 2018).

In the Philippines, the unfavorable school environment on indigenous language use has amplified the effect of language attitude on language use. The discrimination against indigenous people at school is rampant (Eduardo & Gabriel, 2021; Cucio & Roldan, 2020; Victor & Yano, 2016). Lumads in the provinces of Mindanao face inequality, cultural discrimination, and misrepresentation at school (Magdadaro & Sacramento, 2022). In Camarines Sur, students continuously experience discrimination from teachers, students, and schools due to their ethnicity (Magdadaro & Sacramento, 2022). These unwanted school environments have strengthened the negative effect of non-appreciation of indigenous language on its decreased usage by the students (Katerin, et al., 2023).

Locally, Indigenous students at a college in Davao del Sur faced discrimination due to their manner of speaking and self-expression. They were derogatorily referred to as "mountain people" and mocked for using their native language. According to Montecalvo et al. (2023) in their unpublished study, these students would go to restrooms to answer calls from their parents in their native language to avoid ridicule. This situation is alarming, as it fosters shame in Indigenous students about using their native language at school, potentially leading to the demise of the language.

However, the Department of Education (DepEd) is taking steps to eliminate discrimination against Indigenous peoples by recognizing and supporting Indigenous education initiatives, promoting partnerships with Indigenous communities, adopting a rights-based approach, co-managing schools with communities, and implementing affirmative action policies (Cucio & Roldan, 2020). The Department of Education's MTB-MLE policy, implemented in 2012, mandates using students' first languages as the medium of instruction from Kindergarten to Grade 3. Despite initial teacher hesitation and a preference for English, the lack of teaching materials in Indigenous languages also hampers effective implementation (Esteron, 2020). Teachers adapt by code-switching and emphasizing cultural relevance (Russel & Aporbo, 2022).

With the ongoing effort to preserve Indigenous languages in Philippine schools, research on how school culture can affect the relationship between Indigenous students' attitude towards their language and their use of it is found wanting. Thus, this study aimed to investigate the moderating effect of school culture on the relationship of language attitude and usage among the college indigenous people. Understanding and supporting indigenous communities by preserving their languages and cultures will create inclusive classrooms embracing diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds, ultimately benefiting all students. This approach ensures respect and value for Indigenous students' identities while safeguarding their languages and traditions; it is crucial to study how accepting the school culture towards Indigenous languages.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the moderating effect of school culture on the relationship between Indigenous students' attitudes toward their language and their usage of the language. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the level of language attitude of Indigenous students in terms of:
 - 1.1. cognitive aspect;
 - 1.2. affective aspect; and
 - 1.3. and behavioral aspect?
2. What is the level of language use of Indigenous students in terms of:
 - 2.1. personal connection to indigenous language;
 - 2.2. language use in daily life;
 - 2.3. personal commitment to language preservation; and
 - 2.4. and community identity and language?
3. What is the indigenous student's level of perception regarding their school culture in terms of:
 - 3.1. curriculum;
 - 3.2. instruction; and
 - 3.3. and pattern of communication?
4. Does indigenous language attitude influence indigenous language use?
5. Does school culture have a moderating effect on the relationship between indigenous language attitude and indigenous language use?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive regression research design using moderation analysis. According to Kumar (2024), descriptive research summarizes data characteristics, allowing researchers to understand patterns and relationships within the data set. This approach utilizes a quantitative method aimed at the systematic investigation of social phenomena using statistical or numerical data (Watson, 2015). Regression analysis is a statistical tool for investigating relationships between variables (Beers, 2024; Sykes, 1993). Typically, the researcher seeks to ascertain the causal effect of one variable upon another. Moderation analysis examines whether the strength or direction of the relationship between an independent variable (IV) and a dependent variable (DV) is influenced by a

moderator variable (Wormuth, 2024; Memon et al., 2019). This allows researchers to understand not just if a relationship exists, but under what conditions it is stronger or weaker.

In this study, moderation analysis was employed to determine the causal relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Specifically, this study sought to ascertain the effect of indigenous language attitudes on indigenous language use. This involved collecting data on individuals' attitudes towards their indigenous languages and their actual usage patterns. The quantitative approach ensures that the investigation is systematic and the relationships between variables are statistically validated. Moreover, the study aimed to investigate the moderating effect of school culture on the causal relationship between indigenous language attitudes and indigenous language use. School culture, defined by the collective norms, values, and practices within an educational institution, could potentially influence how strongly attitudes towards indigenous languages translate into actual usage. For instance, a school culture that actively promotes and supports indigenous language use might strengthen the positive relationship between favorable language attitudes and language use. On the other hand, a school culture that does not prioritize indigenous languages might weaken this relationship. By employing moderation analysis, the study will test whether the strength or direction of the relationship between indigenous language attitudes (IV) and indigenous language use (DV) changes under different conditions of school culture (the moderator variable). This analysis will involve creating interaction terms between the IV and the moderator variable in the regression model to assess the significance of these interactions (Adekoya, 2015; Descriptive Statistics, 2020; The City College of New York, 2024).

Understanding these dynamics is crucial for developing strategies to promote indigenous language use. If school culture is found to significantly moderate the relationship, it suggests that interventions aimed at fostering a supportive school culture could enhance the effectiveness of efforts to encourage indigenous language use based on positive attitudes. This knowledge can guide policymakers, educators, and community leaders in creating environments that better support the preservation and revitalization of indigenous languages.

Respondents

This study employed indigenous college students enrolled in one of the colleges in Davao Del Sur and they were selected based on the following inclusion and exclusion criteria.

The inclusion criteria were the following: He/she must be an Indigenous college student who is currently enrolled at the College; can speak their indigenous language as their first language; both male and female students were considered for participation. Studies show that Indigenous students enrolled in college often face unique challenges, as studies have documented persistent discrimination in school environments (Milne & Wotherspoon, 2023; Basma et al., 2021). This context underscores the need to address systemic issues impacting Indigenous students' experiences. Shay et al. (2024) emphasize that Indigenous youth voices are seldom prioritized in school policy, highlighting a critical gap in representation and inclusion within institutional frameworks. Further, Indigenous students aged 30-60 years old are included, as proficiency in this language significantly enhances students' participation and engagement in academic and social settings (Whalen, 2022). This criterion recognizes language as a key component of cultural identity and academic involvement. Lastly, respondents must be at least in their second year of stay at the institution, allowing them to become more integrated into the school community. Van der et al. (2023) and Tevis & Britton (2020) note that this prolonged presence provides students with opportunities to engage deeply with peers, faculty, and staff, fostering familiarity with the campus culture, values, and traditions, which are essential for a supportive learning environment. Based on these criteria, there were 55 eligible participants out of the 122 confirmed Indigenous students enrolled for the academic year 2024-2025.

The exclusion criteria were as follows: Indigenous students who are not enrolled at the College, ensuring that all participants are current students and can provide relevant insights based on their experiences within the institution; Indigenous students who cannot speak their indigenous language, as language proficiency is a key component of this study and maintaining the focus on the linguistic aspect of cultural identity was essential; and Indigenous students who have been at the institution for less than one year since these Indigenous students are not acculturated to the school culture, as a shorter residency period may not provide sufficient time for students to fully integrate into the school community and experience its culture, values, and traditions. This refined selection process adheres to the guidelines suggested by Moran and Budiu (2024), Agustin (2021), and Delice (2010), ensuring that the study targets a representative and relevant sample of the Indigenous student population.

Instrument

This study utilized self-constructed questionnaires to have flexibility in tailoring questions for the specific research needs and objectives (Martin, 2006). A group of experts validated these questionnaires to ensure they measured what they intended to measure. A pilot test was also conducted for reliability. Additionally, the results of the negative questions from the questionnaires will be reversed as Suárez Álvarez, et al., (2018) suggested.

For the validity of the research questions, the following are the results from the group of experts.

The table shows that the questionnaires were reviewed by three experts, with two of them rating the validity as "Very Satisfactory" and one as "Satisfactory." The overall rating of 4.27 falls into the "Very Satisfactory" category, demonstrating a strong endorsement of the questionnaires' validity. This high level of agreement among the experts suggests confidence in the questionnaires' ability to accurately

measure the constructs they are designed to assess (Santhosh, et al., 2021). However, the slightly lower rating from Expert 1 indicates that there may be minor areas for improvement.

Table 1. *Validity of the questionnaires*

<i>Validator</i>	<i>Mean Score</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Expert 1	3.33	Satisfactory
Expert 2	4.83	Very Satisfactory
Expert 3	4.66	Very Satisfactory
Overall	4.27	Very Satisfactory

During the pilot-testing of the instruments, 45 participants, having the same characteristics as those of the actual participants of the study, responded to the questionnaires that dealt with the 3 variables which include school culture, indigenous language attitude, and indigenous language use. These answered questionnaires were subjected to the test of reliability by calculating the Cronbach's alpha values of the factors of each variable as well as the Cronbach's alpha value of each variable. A minimum of 0.70 or higher is needed for a questionnaire to pass the test of reliability (Cortina 1993; Bujang, et al. 2018).

The Cronbach's alpha value of the moderator variable, the school culture, was calculated at 0.953.

Table 2. *Cronbach's alpha value for school culture*

<i>Factors</i>	<i>Deleted Items</i>	<i>Cronbach's alpha values</i>
Curriculum	none	0.883
Instruction	none	0.848
Communication pattern	none	0.901
Overall, for School Culture	none	0.9503

The Cronbach's alpha values of the factors that indicate the school culture—including curriculum, instruction, and communication pattern—were calculated at 0.883, 0.848, and .0901 respectively. No items were deleted from the questionnaire on school culture. Two out of the 3 factors that indicate the independent variable, the indigenous language attitude, initially obtained Cronbach's alpha values below 0.70. To improve the value of the cognitive factor, the study removed 4 items from measuring it which resulted in a greater value of 0.716.

Table 3. *Cronbach's value for indigenous language attitude*

<i>Factors</i>	<i>Deleted Items</i>	<i>Cronbach's alpha values</i>
Cognitive	1, 5, 6, 7	0.716
Affective	none	0.873
Behavioural	1, 2, 4, 5, 12, 13	0.704
Overall, for Indigenous Language Attitude	1, 2, 4, 5, 5, 12, 13	0.9503

Six items were also removed under the behavioral factor, which also resulted in an improved value of 0.704. The affective factor got a value of 0.823. Overall, the indigenous language attitude obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.905. The Cronbach's value of the dependent variable, indigenous language use, was calculated at 0.938. One item under the factor described as language in daily life was removed to improve the factor's Cronbach's alpha value from less than 0.70 to 0.779.

Table 4. *Cronbach's alpha value for indigenous language use*

<i>Factors</i>	<i>Deleted Items</i>	<i>Cronbach's alpha values</i>
Personal connection to indigenous life	none	0.877
Language in daily life	10	0.779
Personal commitment to language preservation	none	0.887
Community identity and language	none	0.860
Overall, for Indigenous Language Use	10	0.938

The Cronbach's alpha values of the other factors that indicate the indigenous language use—including personal connection to indigenous language, personal commitment to language preservation, and community identity and language—were calculated at 0.877, 0.887, and 0.860, respectively.

The questionnaires used the Likert scale, a psychometric tool commonly used in educational and social sciences research to measure attitudes or opinions (Joshi et al., 2015; Nadler et al., 2015). It allowed participants to assess their level of agreement or disagreement with a series of statements on a metric scale, typically ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree" (Joshi et al., 2015). When the statements are negatively stated, the interpretation of the scales will be reversed. If the statement in the questionnaire is negative, a response of 1 would mean strongly agree, 2 agree, 3 disagree, and 4 would mean strongly disagree. According to Gordon Wolf et al. (2019), the instrument had slightly better psychometric properties with a 4-point response option, although the estimates for both response options were acceptable. From a statistical perspective, there was no rationale to switch to a 6-point response option when a 4-point response option was already in place. Therefore, the questionnaires for this study used an interval scale (Joshi et al., 2015) since

results are combined to create a composite score and 4-point response options in the questionnaires.

These questionnaires are for indigenous language attitude with its subscales; Cognitive aspect, Affective Aspect, and Behavioral Aspect. The questions are self-made to ensure the alignment of the study's objectives and purposes (Robbins,1999). In evaluating the language attitude of the indigenous students, the following range of means with their descriptions were used.

Table 5. Range of Means, Descriptive Equivalent and Interpretation for Indigenous Language Attitude

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree (1)	This means a strong negative sentiment towards indigenous language attitude. This suggests that indigenous students have a highly negative attitude towards their indigenous language. Possible reasons could include experiences of stigma, a lack of support for using their language, or internalized negative beliefs about the value of their language. This range highlights a critical area needing attention to foster a more positive and supportive environment for indigenous language use and pride in terms of cognitive, affective, and behavioral.
1.75 - 2.49	Disagree (2)	This means a negative sentiment towards indigenous language attitude. This suggests that indigenous students somewhat feel a negative attitude towards their indigenous language. They may face barriers or challenges that discourage positive attitudes, such as limited opportunities to use their language, negative peer or societal attitudes, or insufficient institutional support in terms of cognitive, affective, and behavioral..
2.50 -3.24	Agree (3)	This means somewhat positive sentiment towards indigenous language attitude. Indigenous students generally feel positive about their language, indicating a supportive environment to some extent. However, there is still room for improvement in promoting stronger positive attitudes and increasing the visibility and use of the indigenous language within the school in terms of cognitive, affective, and behavioral..
3.25 -4.00	Strongly Agree (4)	This means a strong positive sentiment towards indigenous language attitude. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that indigenous students feel highly positive about their indigenous language. They likely experience strong support and encouragement for using their language, contributing to a sense of pride and cultural identity. This reflects a school culture that highly values linguistic diversity and actively promotes positive attitudes towards indigenous languages in terms of cognitive, affective, and behavioral.

The following range of means, with descriptions, were used to evaluate the language attitude of the indigenous students in terms of cognitive aspect.

Table 6. Range of Means, Descriptive Equivalent, and Interpretation for Indigenous Language Attitude in terms of Cognitive Aspect

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
3.25 -4.00.	Strongly Agree (4)	This means a strong positive sentiment towards indigenous language attitude cognitively. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that indigenous students deeply value their language, actively work to preserve and promote it, and confidently share it, inspiring respect. They integrate it into daily communication at school, recognizing its importance for maintaining cultural identity.
2.50 -3.24	Agree (3)	This means a somewhat positive sentiment towards indigenous language attitude cognitively. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that indigenous students acknowledge the importance of their language and appreciate its role in community identity. They participate in cultural events, share the language confidently, and strive to integrate it into daily communication, while recognizing the benefits of dominant languages.
1.75 - 2.49	Disagree (2)	This means a limited understanding of indigenous language value. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that indigenous students recognize their language's existence but do not actively engage with or promote it. They prefer dominant languages, feeling these are more beneficial, and may not confidently share their indigenous language.
1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree (1)	This means a negative sentiment towards indigenous language attitude cognitively. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that indigenous students perceive their language as less valuable compared to dominant languages. They rarely engage with or promote it, do not take pride in it, and are unlikely to inspire respect for it, contributing to its decline.

The following range of means, with descriptions, were used to evaluate the language attitude of the Indigenous students in terms of affective aspect.

Table 7. Range of Means, Descriptive Equivalent, and Interpretation for Indigenous Language attitude in terms of Affective Aspect

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
3.25 -4.00.	Strongly	This means a strong positive sentiment towards indigenous languages affectively. If the mean score falls

	Agree (4)	within this range, it suggests that indigenous students deeply value their language. They feel proud, confident, and supported when using it, believe it is respected by peers, and integrate it confidently into daily communication. They feel emotionally attached to their language and comfortable hearing and speaking it, reinforcing their cultural identity.
2.50 -3.24	Agree (3)	This means a somewhat positive sentiment towards indigenous languages affectively. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that indigenous students generally value their language. They feel mostly proud and confident using it, believe it is often respected by peers, and try to integrate it into daily communication. They have a positive emotional attachment to their language and feel comfortable hearing and speaking it, supporting their cultural identity.
1.75 - 2.49	Disagree (2)	This means a limited sentiment towards indigenous languages affectively. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that indigenous students have reservations about their language's value. They may feel less confident and supported using it, believe it is not always respected by peers, and prioritize dominant languages. They have a weaker emotional attachment to their language and feel less comfortable hearing and speaking it, reflecting a lower cultural identity.
1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree (1)	This means a negative sentiment towards indigenous languages affectively . If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that indigenous students do not value their language. They feel uncomfortable and unsupported using it, believe it is not respected by peers, and prefer dominant languages. They lack emotional attachment to their language and feel uncomfortable hearing and speaking it, undermining their cultural identity.

The following range of means, with descriptions, were used to evaluate the language attitude of the Indigenous students in terms of behavioral aspects.

Table 8. *Range of Means, Descriptive Equivalent, and Interpretation for Indigenous Language attitude in terms of Behavioral Aspect*

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
3.25 -4.00.	Strongly Agree (4)	This means a strong positive sentiment toward Indigenous language attitude behavior. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students actively value their Indigenous language, engaging in activities to promote it and integrate it into their daily lives. They show openness to learning and use their language thoughtfully, even in formal settings. They balance its use with dominant languages, demonstrating pride in their heritage and a sense of belonging when using their Indigenous language.
2.50 -3.24	Agree (3)	This means a somewhat positive sentiment toward Indigenous language attitude behavior. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students recognize the importance of their Indigenous language and participate in activities to support its preservation. They are mindful of its use in various contexts and are comfortable integrating it alongside dominant languages. They may prefer dominant languages for practical reasons but still appreciate the cultural value of their Indigenous language.
1.75 - 2.49	Disagree (2)	This means a limited understanding or appreciation of Indigenous language. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students may not actively engage with their Indigenous language and might prioritize dominant languages in daily communication. They recognize the language's existence but may not feel confident using it or see its relevance in certain contexts, such as formal school settings or social interactions.
1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree (1)	This means a negative sentiment toward Indigenous language attitude behavior. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students may view their Indigenous language as less relevant or valuable compared to dominant languages. They are unlikely to participate in activities that promote the language, rarely use it in daily life, and may avoid situations where it is expected, contributing to its decline and potential loss within their community.

These questionnaires are for indigenous language use with its subscales; Personal Connection to Indigenous Language, Language Use in Daily Life, Personal Commitment to Language Preservation, and Community Identity and Language.

Table 9. *Range of Means, Descriptive Equivalent and Interpretation for Indigenous Language Use*

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
3.25 -4.00.	Strongly Agree (4)	This means that indigenous students confidently use their indigenous language at school. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests a high level of support and acceptance for indigenous language use within the school. Students likely feel proud and encouraged to speak their indigenous language, reflecting a school culture that highly values linguistic diversity and actively promotes indigenous language use. This environment likely includes strong institutional support, resources, and policies that foster a positive and inclusive atmosphere for indigenous language speakers in terms of personal communication to indigenous language, language use in daily life, personal commitment to language preservation, and community identity and language.
2.50 -3.24	Agree (3)	This means that indigenous students do use their indigenous language at school. This indicates that there are some opportunities and a certain level of acceptance for indigenous language use within the school environment. While this is a positive sign, it also suggests there is still room for improvement in making the

		use of indigenous languages more widespread and fully integrated into the school's daily life and activities in terms of personal communication to indigenous language, language use in daily life, personal commitment to language preservation, and community identity and language..
1.75 - 2.49	Disagree (2)	This means that indigenous students generally do not use their indigenous language at school. This could indicate a lack of opportunities or resources to use their language, or it may reflect a school culture that does not encourage or facilitate indigenous language use in terms of personal communication to indigenous language, language use in daily life, personal commitment to language preservation, and community identity and language...
1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree (1)	This means that indigenous students strongly oppose the use of their indigenous language at school. This opposition could stem from various factors, such as feeling discouraged or unwelcome to use their language, fear of discrimination, or a lack of institutional support for indigenous language use. This range reflects a significant barrier to the integration of indigenous languages in the school environment and suggests a need for substantial efforts to create a more supportive atmosphere for language use in terms of personal communication to indigenous language, language use in daily life, personal commitment to language preservation, and community identity and language.

The following range of means were used to evaluate the language use of the Indigenous students in Terms of Personal Connection to Indigenous Language

Table 10. *Range of Means, Descriptive Equivalent and Interpretation for Indigenous Language Use in Terms of Personal Connection to Indigenous Language*

Range of Means	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
3.25 -4.00.	Strongly Agree (4)	This means that indigenous students have strong personal connection to indigenous language. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students firmly believe that using their indigenous language is a fundamental aspect of expressing their cultural identity and who they are as persons. Moreover, using their indigenous language firmly bonds them with their community and highly relates them to their ancestors.
2.50 -3.24	Agree (3)	This means that indigenous students have some personal connection to indigenous language. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students have some belief that using their indigenous language is a fundamental aspect of expressing their cultural identity and who they are as persons. Moreover, using their indigenous language bonds them with their community and relates them to their ancestors
1.75 - 2.49	Disagree (2)	This means that indigenous students have weak personal connection to indigenous language. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students rarely believe that using their indigenous language is a fundamental aspect of expressing their cultural identity and who they are as persons. Moreover, using their indigenous language poorly bonds them with their community and vaguely relates them to their ancestors.
1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree (1)	This means that indigenous students have no personal connection to indigenous language. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students do not believe that using their indigenous language is a fundamental aspect of expressing their cultural identity and who they are as persons. Moreover, using their indigenous language neither bonds them with their community nor relates them to their ancestors.

The following range of means, with descriptions, were used to evaluate the language use of the Indigenous students in Terms of Language Use in Daily Life.

Table 11. *Range of Means, Descriptive Equivalent and Interpretation for Indigenous Language Use in terms of Language Use in Daily Life*

Range of Means	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
3.25 -4.00.	Strongly Agree (4)	This means that indigenous students have greatly regular use of the indigenous language in daily life. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students always use the indigenous language in their day-to-day conversations and conversations within their families are always based on their indigenous language. Moreover, they always express their thoughts and feelings in their indigenous language and actively seek opportunities on how to incorporate their indigenous language in various circumstances of their lives.
2.50 -3.24	Agree (3)	This means that indigenous students have regular use of the indigenous language in daily life. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students oftentimes use the indigenous language in their day-to-day conversations and conversations within their families are many times based on their indigenous language. Moreover, they oftentimes express their thoughts and feelings in their indigenous language and seek opportunities on how to incorporate their indigenous language in various circumstances of their lives.
1.75 - 2.49	Disagree (2)	This means that indigenous students rarely use their indigenous language in daily life. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students rarely use the indigenous language in their day-to-day conversations and conversations within their families are scarcely based on their indigenous language. Moreover, they occasionally express their thoughts and feelings in their indigenous language and poorly seek opportunities on how to incorporate their indigenous language in various circumstances of their lives
1.00 - 1.74	Strongly	This means that indigenous students do not use their indigenous language in daily life. If the mean score

Disagree (1)	falls within this range, it suggests that students never use the indigenous language in their day-to-day conversations and conversations within their families are not based on their indigenous language. Moreover, they do not express their thoughts and feelings in their indigenous language and never seek opportunities on how to incorporate their indigenous language in various circumstances of their lives
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The following range of means, with descriptions, were used to evaluate the language use of the indigenous students in Terms of Personal Commitment to Language Preservation.

Table 12. *Range of Means, Descriptive Equivalent and Interpretation for Indigenous Language Use in terms of Personal Commitment to Language Preservation*

Range of Means	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
3.25 -4.00.	Strongly Agree (4)	This means that indigenous students have deep personal commitment to language preservation. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students deeply commit to ensure future generations to use their indigenous language. Moreover, they always see the importance of helping keep the indigenous language alive and strongly prioritize speaking the indigenous language even when communicating in multicultural settings.
2.50 -3.24	Agree (3)	This means that indigenous students have some personal commitment to language preservation. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students commit to ensure future generations to use their indigenous language. Moreover, they see the importance of helping keep the indigenous language alive and prioritize speaking the indigenous language even when communicating in multicultural settings.
1.75 - 2.49	Disagree (2)	This means that indigenous students have less concern about language preservation. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students commit to ensure future generations to use their indigenous language. Moreover, they seldom see the importance of helping keep the indigenous language alive and reluctantly speak the indigenous language in multicultural settings.
1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree (1)	This means that indigenous students do not about language preservation. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students do not commit to ensure future generations to use their indigenous language. Moreover, they never see the importance of helping keep the indigenous language alive and do not speak the indigenous language in multicultural settings.

The following range of means, with descriptions, were used to evaluate the language use of the indigenous students in Terms of Community Identity and Language.

Table 13. *Range of Means, Descriptive Equivalent and Interpretation for Indigenous Language Use in terms of Community Identity and Language*

Range of Means	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
3.25 -4.00.	Strongly Agree (4)	This means that indigenous students have strong sense of community and language. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students firmly believe that using indigenous language enhances the sense of unity and belongingness within their community, and helps them show to the world who they are as an indigenous community.
2.50 -3.24	Agree (3)	This means that indigenous students have some sense of community and language. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students sometimes believe that using indigenous language enhances the sense of unity and belongingness within their community, and at times helps them show to the world who they are as an indigenous community.
1.75 - 2.49	Disagree (2)	This means that indigenous students have little sense of community and language. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students rarely believe that using indigenous language enhances the sense of unity and belongingness within their community, and insignificantly helps them show to the world who they are as an indigenous community.
1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree (1)	This means that indigenous students do not have sense of community and language. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students never believe that using indigenous language enhances the sense of unity and belongingness within their community, and does not help them show to the world who they are as an indigenous community.

These questionnaires are for School Culture with its subscales; Curriculum, Instruction, and Pattern of Communication. The questions are self-made to ensure the alignment of the study's objectives and purposes (Robbins,1999). In evaluating the school culture, the following range of means with its descriptions were used.

Table 14. *Range of Means, Descriptive Equivalent, and Interpretation for School Culture*

Range of Means	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
3.25 -4.00.	Strongly Agree (4)	This means a strong positive sentiment towards school culture. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that indigenous students feel highly positive about the school environment. They likely feel valued, respected, and well-integrated into the school community. This reflects a highly inclusive and supportive school culture that effectively meets the needs of its indigenous students in terms of

2.50 -3.24	Agree (3)	curriculum, instruction, and patterns of communication. This means somewhat positive sentiment towards school culture. Indigenous students might feel generally positive, though there could still be room for improvement. This indicates that while the school environment is supportive and inclusive to an extent, further efforts could enhance this positivity and ensure a more healthy sense of belonging and respect for cultural diversity in terms of curriculum, instruction, and patterns of communication..
1.75 - 2.49	Disagree (2)	This means negative sentiment. Indigenous students might feel somewhat negative about the school culture, indicating dissatisfaction but not as intense as the "Strongly Disagree" range. This could involve occasional cultural misunderstandings or insufficient support. Addressing these areas could help mitigate the negative feelings and improve the overall school experience in terms of curriculum, instruction, and patterns of communication..
1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree (1)	This means a strong negative sentiment towards school culture. Indigenous students may feel the school environment is highly negative, suggesting issues such as feeling unwelcome, facing discrimination, or experiencing cultural insensitivity. This range reflects a need for significant changes to address these critical concerns in terms of curriculum, instruction, and patterns of communication.

In evaluating the school culture, the following range of means with its descriptions were used in terms of Curriculum.

Table 15. *Range of Means, Descriptive Equivalent and Interpretation for School Culture in terms of Curriculum*

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
3.25 -4.00.	Strongly Agree (4)	This means that the school strongly incorporates indigenous languages and cultures into its curriculum. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students believe the curriculum effectively promotes cross-cultural understanding, preserves indigenous languages, and integrates indigenous perspectives across various subjects. Students feel satisfied with the inclusion of specialized courses, interdisciplinary projects, and experiential learning opportunities related to indigenous languages.
2.50 -3.24	Agree (3)	This means that the school moderately incorporates indigenous languages and cultures into its curriculum. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students recognize some effort in promoting cross-cultural understanding and preserving indigenous languages. While the curriculum includes indigenous perspectives and interdisciplinary projects, the commitment is not as strong or consistent as in the higher range.
1.75 - 2.49	Disagree (2)	This means that the school has limited incorporation of indigenous languages and cultures into its curriculum. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students rarely see efforts to promote cross-cultural understanding or preserve indigenous languages. The inclusion of indigenous perspectives and interdisciplinary projects is minimal, indicating a need for greater integration and support.
1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree (1)	This means that the school does not incorporate indigenous languages and cultures into its curriculum. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students do not see any efforts to promote cross-cultural understanding or preserve indigenous languages. The curriculum lacks indigenous perspectives, interdisciplinary projects, and experiential learning opportunities, highlighting a significant gap in cultural responsiveness.

In evaluating the school culture, the following range of means with its descriptions were used in terms of Instructions

Table 16. *Range of Means, Descriptive Equivalent and Interpretation for School Culture in terms of Instruction*

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
3.25 -4.00.	Strongly Agree (4)	This means that teachers actively integrate and support indigenous languages in instruction. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students feel their teachers make significant efforts to incorporate indigenous words and phrases, encourage questions about indigenous languages, and celebrate their use. Teachers in this range are seen as valuing and promoting the cultural significance and preservation of indigenous languages.
2.50 -3.24	Agree (3)	This means that teachers moderately integrate and support indigenous languages in instruction. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students see some effort from their teachers to include indigenous language elements and support their learning. Teachers in this range recognize the importance of indigenous languages, but the integration and encouragement are less consistent compared to the higher range.
1.75 - 2.49	Disagree (2)	This means that teachers have limited integration and support for indigenous languages in instruction. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students rarely see efforts from their teachers to incorporate or promote indigenous languages. The support for learning and using indigenous languages is minimal, indicating a need for more intentional efforts in instruction.
1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree (1)	This means that teachers do not integrate or support indigenous languages in instruction. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students do not feel their teachers acknowledge or value indigenous languages. There is a significant lack of effort to incorporate indigenous language elements, support learning, or recognize their cultural importance in the classroom.

In evaluating the school culture, the following range of means with its descriptions were used in terms of Patterns of Communication.

Table 17. Range of Means, Descriptive Equivalent and Interpretation for School Culture in terms of Patterns of Communication

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
3.25 - 4.00.	Strongly Agree (4)	This means that the school actively promotes and values Indigenous languages in its communication patterns. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students believe Indigenous languages are well-represented and celebrated in activities, events, and daily school life. Students from Indigenous backgrounds feel supported and encouraged to share their languages, creating an inclusive and respectful environment. There are ample opportunities for students to engage in projects supporting language revitalization, and resources are readily available for learning Indigenous languages.
2.50 - 3.24	Agree (3)	This means that the school makes a moderate effort to include indigenous languages in its communication patterns. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students see some representation and celebration of Indigenous languages in activities and events. There is occasional support for students to share their languages and participate in language revitalization projects. While the environment is generally inclusive, the efforts to promote and support Indigenous languages are less consistent than in the higher range.
1.75 - 2.49	Disagree (2)	This means that the school has limited efforts to incorporate Indigenous languages into its communication patterns. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students rarely see Indigenous languages represented or celebrated in school activities and events. There is minimal support for Indigenous students to share their languages, and few opportunities for involvement in language revitalization projects. The environment may lack inclusivity and respect for Indigenous languages.
1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree (1)	This means that the school does not include Indigenous languages in its communication patterns. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students do not see any representation or celebration of Indigenous languages in school activities, events, or daily life. There is no support for Indigenous students to share their languages, and no opportunities for language revitalization projects. The environment is not inclusive or respectful of Indigenous languages, indicating a significant need for change.

The initial draft of the research instrument was submitted to the research adviser for feedback, which included comments, suggestions, and recommendations aimed at improving its presentation. These corrections were subsequently integrated. The revised version was then reviewed by three panels of experts for further refinement. Final adjustments were made by incorporating the expert validators' corrections and suggestions before data collection commenced. Additionally, a pilot test of the research instrument was conducted with indigenous students from a school in Davao Del Sur, who were not part of the study's respondents. The survey questionnaire used in the pilot test underwent reliability and content validity assessment using the Internal Consistency Method. This method was deemed appropriate as the test consisted of dichotomously scored items, where examinees either passed or failed each item. The computed reliability of the instrument was found to be greater than 0.70, using Cronbach's Alpha (Mohamad et al., 2015).

Procedure

The following steps were undertaken by the researcher in the conduct of the study.

The researcher sent a permission letter to the Dean of the Graduate School of Cor Jesu College, Inc., and the study was reviewed by the Review Ethics Committee (REC). After the review, the study was approved.

The researcher sent a permission letter to the National Commission on Indigenous Peoples (NCIP), and approval was granted.

A permission letter was also sent to one of the colleges in Davao del Sur for the pilot testing of the study. Once approved, the data was personally collected through surveys.

During the pilot testing, the researcher ensured that the work of the teachers and classes were not disrupted. The researcher also addressed any questions or clarifications from the respondents. Once the respondents had completed the questionnaire, the researcher collected all the completed surveys.

After successfully collecting the questionnaires from the pilot testing, the validity and reliability of the survey were assessed. This process involved refining the questions to ensure they were relevant to the study and making any necessary adjustments to the selected respondents.

After the pilot testing, the researcher submitted another permission letter to the school where the study was conducted. Once approval was granted, the questionnaires were distributed to the enrolled IP students and collected all the completed surveys.

The responses in the survey questionnaire were kept confidential, in line with the agreement between the respondents and the researcher, ensuring the privacy of the respondents' identities and answers. Based on the results of the statistical analysis, the collected data was organized and tabulated, with the help of a statistical consultant.

Data Analysis

This study made use of frequency distribution tables to show the distribution of the three variables of the study. The following statistical

tools were used in analyzing the data and testing the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance;

Mean scores were calculated to determine the levels of language attitude, language use, and school culture (Ramesh, et al., 2018).

Moderated analysis was employed in order to determine the main and moderating effects of the model (Sykes, 1993).

The specific function to be used is as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X + \beta_2 Z + \beta_3 XZ$$

where Y is indigenous language use

X is language attitude of indigenous students

Z is school culture

XZ is the interaction term

β_1 , β_2 measure the main effects of the model and β_3 measures the effect of the moderator variable.

Ethical Considerations

To ensure the ethical conduct of the study titled "The Moderating Effect of School Culture on the Relationship of Language Attitude and Language Use," the study observed informed consent and voluntary participation, maintained anonymity and confidentiality, and protected the data and privacy of the participants. By following these best practices, the study ensured respect of the rights and dignity of the indigenous people involved and contributed to the advancement of knowledge responsibly and ethically. The gathered data were sealed in a box that only the researcher can access. It will be disposed of after two years by burning it.

Informed Consent. This contained the purpose of the study, the time element, and the procedures of the study. It also included an explanation of the voluntary involvement of the participants which they signed before the conduct of the study. It was also explained to the participants if they would withdraw from their participation, their decision would be accepted. The risks and benefits and the information about the researcher were explained to the respondents as well. Further, the researcher wrote and asked permission from the school head of the school where the respondents were enrolled.

Anonymity and Confidentiality. To maintain anonymity and confidentiality, the study ensured that no identifying information was collected or stored. This included avoiding the collection of direct identifiers such as names, addresses, or contact information (Seattle University, n.d.). If indirect identifiers like gender, race, or age are collected, the study ensured that these do not compromise the anonymity of the participants (Understanding Confidentiality and Anonymity, n.d.).

Data Protection. To protect the data and privacy of the participants, the study implemented robust data protection measures. This included ensuring that data was stored securely, access was restricted to authorized personnel, and data will be properly disposed of upon completion of the study. Participants were also informed about how their data will be used and protected (European University Institute, 2022).

By adhering to these ethical considerations, the study on "The Moderating Effect of School Culture on the Relationship of Language Attitude and Language Use" was conducted in a manner that respects the participants and maintains the integrity of the research.

Results and Discussion

Level of Language Attitude of Indigenous Students

This study explored the Indigenous students' attitudes toward their language, focusing on three main areas: cognitive, affective, and behavioral. The cognitive aspect investigates students' beliefs and perceptions about their language's value and role. The affective aspect examines their emotional connections, such as pride and attachment to their language. Lastly, the behavioral aspect considers how these attitudes influence their actions, like their willingness to use and advocate for the language. Together, these findings provide insight into the overall level of language attitude among indigenous students and reveal how their beliefs, feelings, and actions contribute to language use and preservation. These findings are presented in Table 18.

Table 18. Results on Mean Scores of Subscales and Scale for Indigenous People's Attitude

Subscale	Mean Score	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
Cognitive Aspect	3.05	Agree	This means a somewhat positive sentiment towards indigenous language attitude cognitively. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that indigenous students acknowledge the importance of their language and appreciate its role in community identity. They participate in cultural events, share the language confidently, and strive to integrate it into daily communication, while recognizing the benefits of dominant languages.
Affective Aspect	3.17	Agree	This means a somewhat positive sentiment towards indigenous languages affectively. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that indigenous students generally value their

Behavioral Aspect	2.81	Agree	language. They feel mostly proud and confident using it, believe it is often respected by peers, and try to integrate it into daily communication. They have a positive emotional attachment to their language and feel comfortable hearing and speaking it, supporting their cultural identity. This means a somewhat positive sentiment toward Indigenous language attitude behavior. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students recognize the importance of their Indigenous language and participate in activities to support its preservation. They are mindful of its use in various contexts and are comfortable integrating it alongside dominant languages. They may prefer dominant languages for practical reasons but still appreciate the cultural value of their Indigenous language.
Scale for Indigenous People's Attitude	3.01	Agree	This means a negative sentiment towards indigenous language attitude. This suggests that indigenous students somewhat feel a negative attitude towards their indigenous language. They may face barriers or challenges that discourage positive attitudes, such as limited opportunities to use their language, negative peer or societal attitudes, or insufficient institutional support in terms of cognitive, affective, and behavioral..

Table 18 shows the mean scores of subscales and scales for indigenous language attitude. The mean score of the scale for indigenous language attitude is 3.01 with a descriptive equivalent of "agree," which means that Indigenous students somewhat feel a positive attitude towards their indigenous language. The mean scores of subscales for the cognitive aspect, affective aspect, and behavioural are 3.05, 3.17, and 2.81 respectively—all with the descriptive equivalent of "agree," indicating that Indigenous students show a positive but varied engagement with their language, demonstrating pride, confidence, and recognition of its importance for cultural identity and community, while balancing the use of dominant languages for broader connections.

Level of Language Use of Indigenous Students

This study examines the level of language use among indigenous students, focusing on their personal and communal connections to their indigenous language. First, it looks at their personal connection to the language, exploring how meaningful and relevant it feels in their lives. The analysis then shifts to the frequency and context of language use in daily life, considering how often they incorporate their language into everyday interactions. Additionally, the section discusses students' commitment to preserving their language, capturing the extent of their dedication to its survival for future generations. Finally, it delves into how community identity influences language use, highlighting the role of cultural and social ties in sustaining indigenous language practices. Together, these findings provide a well-rounded perspective on the factors that influence indigenous students' language use and contribute to ongoing efforts in language preservation. These findings are presented in Table 19.

Table 19. Mean Scores of Subscales and Scale for Indigenous Language Use

Subscale	Mean Score	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
Personal Connection to Indigenous Language	3.40	Strongly Agree	This means that indigenous students have strong personal connection to indigenous language. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students firmly believe that using their indigenous language is a fundamental aspect of expressing their cultural identity and who they are as persons. Moreover, using their indigenous language firmly bonds them with their community and highly relates them to their ancestors.
Language Use in Daily Life	2.82	Strongly Agree	This means that indigenous students have greatly regular use of the indigenous language in daily life. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students always use the indigenous language in their day-to-day conversations and conversations within their families are always based on their indigenous language. Moreover, they always express their thoughts and feelings in their indigenous language and actively seek opportunities on how to incorporate their indigenous language in various circumstances of their lives.
Personal Commitment to Language Preservation	3.33	Strongly Agree	This means that indigenous students have deep personal commitment to language preservation. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students deeply commit to ensure future generations to use their indigenous language. Moreover, they always see the importance of helping keep the indigenous language alive and strongly prioritize speaking the indigenous language even when communicating in multicultural settings.
Community Identity and Language	3.36	Strongly Agree	This means that indigenous students have strong sense of community and language. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students firmly believe that using indigenous language enhances the sense of unity and belongingness within their community, and helps them show to the world who they are as an indigenous community.
Scale for Indigenous People's Attitude	3.24	Agree	This means that indigenous students do use their indigenous language at school. This indicates that there are some opportunities and a certain level of acceptance for indigenous language use within the school environment. While this is a positive sign, it also suggests there is still room for improvement in making the use of indigenous languages more widespread and fully integrated into the school's daily life and activities in terms of personal communication to indigenous language, language use in daily life, personal commitment to language preservation, and community identity and language..

Table 19 shows the mean scores of subscales and scales for indigenous language use. The mean score of the scale for indigenous language use is 3.24 with a descriptive equivalent of agree which means that indigenous students use their indigenous language many times in their daily lives.

The mean scores of subscales for a personal connection to indigenous language, personal commitment to language preservation, and community identity and language are 3.40, 3.33, and 3.36 respectively—all with the descriptive equivalent of strongly agree which means that Indigenous students have a profound personal connection to their language, reflecting a deep commitment to its preservation, a strong bond with their community, and a sense of cultural identity and unity. The mean score of the subscale for language use in daily life is 2.82 with a descriptive rating of agree which means that indigenous students oftentimes use the indigenous language in their day-to-day conversations and conversations within their families are many times based on their indigenous language.

Level of Perception Regarding Their School Culture

This study explores Indigenous students' perceptions of their school culture, focusing on how it may impact their language and cultural identity. The analysis begins with students' views on the curriculum, examining whether it includes and respects their indigenous language and heritage. Next, it considers their experiences with instruction, looking at whether teaching methods encourage or discourage the use of their language. Finally, it assesses the patterns of communication within the school environment, including how language is used and valued in interactions among students, teachers, and staff. Together, these insights shed light on how school culture supports or limits indigenous language preservation, highlighting areas that may strengthen students' connection to their heritage. These findings are presented in Table 20.

Table 20. Mean Scores of Subscales and Scale for Level of Perception on School Culture

<i>Subscale</i>	<i>Mean Score</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Curriculum	3.17	Agree	This means that the school moderately incorporates indigenous languages and cultures into its curriculum. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students recognize some effort in promoting cross-cultural understanding and preserving indigenous languages. While the curriculum includes indigenous perspectives and interdisciplinary projects, the commitment is not as strong or consistent as in the higher range.
Instruction	3.17	Agree	This means that teachers moderately integrate and support indigenous languages in instruction. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students see some effort from their teachers to include indigenous language elements and support their learning. Teachers in this range recognize the importance of indigenous languages, but the integration and encouragement are less consistent compared to the higher range.
Pattern of Communication	3.18	Agree	This means that the school makes a moderate effort to include indigenous languages in its communication patterns. If the mean score falls within this range, it suggests that students see some representation and celebration of Indigenous languages in activities and events. There is occasional support for students to share their languages and participate in language revitalization projects. While the environment is generally inclusive, the efforts to promote and support Indigenous languages are less consistent than in the higher range.
Scale for School Culture	3.17	Agree	This means somewhat positive sentiment towards school culture. Indigenous students might feel generally positive, though there could still be room for improvement. This indicates that while the school environment is supportive and inclusive to an extent, further efforts could enhance this positivity and ensure a more healthy sense of belonging and respect for cultural diversity in terms of curriculum, instruction, and patterns of communication.

Table 20 shows the mean scores of subscales and scales for school culture. The mean score of the scale for School Culture is 3.17 with a descriptive equivalent of agree which means that indigenous students feel generally positive, though there could still be room for improvement. The mean scores of subscales for curriculum, instruction, and pattern of communication are 3.17, 3.17, and 3.18 respectively—all with the descriptive equivalent of agree which means that the school demonstrates a moderate commitment to incorporating indigenous languages and cultures in its curriculum, instruction, and communication, with noticeable efforts in promoting cross-cultural understanding and language preservation, but with less consistency compared to higher levels of integration and support.

Moderation Estimates of School Culture on the Causal Relationship Between Indigenous People's Language Attitude and Language Usage

This study investigated whether indigenous students' attitudes toward their language influence their actual language use. By analyzing the relationship between students' beliefs, emotions, and behaviors regarding their language and how often they use it, this study aims to clarify how positive or negative attitudes impact language practices. The study then considers the role of school culture as a potential moderating factor, investigating whether elements like curriculum, instructional practices, and communication patterns strengthen or weaken the connection between language attitudes and use. This dual analysis provides insights into how school culture can either support or hinder language preservation efforts, highlighting the ways educational environments contribute to sustaining indigenous languages. These findings are presented in Table 21.

Table 21. *Moderation Estimates of School Culture on the Causal Relationship Between Indigenous People's Attitude and Indigenous Language Use*

	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>p</i>
Indigenous People's Attitude (X)	0.3120	0.105	2.970	0.003
School Culture (Z)	0.0585	0.102	0.575	0.565
Interaction Term (X*Z)	-0.4469	0.225	-1.986	0.047

Table 21 shows the results of the moderated regression analysis. Among others, this study was conducted to determine whether there is a causal relationship between indigenous people's attitude and indigenous language use. Moreover, it aimed to determine if the school culture can moderate the causal relationship between the 2 variables. The results indicate that indigenous people's attitude ($\beta=0.3120$, $p<.05$) had a significant positive effect on indigenous language use.

The results also show that, while school culture does not have a significant effect ($\beta=0.0585$, $p=0.565$) on the indigenous language use, there is a significant interaction ($\beta= -0.4469$, $p=0.047$) between the indigenous people's attitude and school culture. This indicates that school culture does moderate the causal relationship between the indigenous people's attitude and indigenous language use.

Effect of Indigenous People's Language Attitude on Indigenous Language Usage at Different Levels of School Culture

This study examines how indigenous students' attitudes toward their language affect their language use, specifically within the various levels of school culture. The findings aim to clarify the extent to which supportive school environments amplify or diminish the impact of language attitudes on usage, revealing important insights into how educational culture can either strengthen or weaken efforts to preserve indigenous languages. The results are presented in Table 5.

Table 22. *Slope Analysis of the effect of indigenous people's attitude on indigenous language use at the different levels of school culture*

	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>p</i>
Average	0.312	0.108	2.881	0.004
Low(-1SD)	0.508	0.157	3.228	0.001
High(+1SD)	0.116	0.137	0.848	0.897

Table 22 shows the effect of indigenous people's attitudes on indigenous language use at the different levels of school culture. Results show that there is a significant causal relationship between indigenous people's attitudes on indigenous language use at low and average levels of school culture with p-values of 0.004 and 0.001 respectively. However, such a causal relationship becomes insignificant at a high level of school culture with a p-value of 0.397. These results suggest that while positive attitudes towards Indigenous languages remain important, they may not be enough to ensure that these languages are actively used and preserved in stronger school cultures.

Level of Language Attitude of Indigenous Students

This discussion explores the various dimensions of language attitude among Indigenous students, focusing on the affective, cognitive, and behavioral aspects. By examining survey results, insights can be gained into the pride, confidence, and engagement these students have towards their indigenous language, which plays a crucial role in maintaining their cultural heritage and identity.

The mean score of the scale for indigenous language attitude (3.01) suggests a generally positive attitude towards their language, although this sentiment varies across different dimensions. These findings indicate that students feel a positive but varied engagement with their language, showing pride, confidence, and recognition of its importance for cultural identity and community while balancing the use of dominant languages for broader connections.

Cognitive Aspect

The subscale mean score of indigenous language attitude in terms of the cognitive aspect (3.05) suggests a somewhat positive sentiment towards school culture cognitively. This indicates that indigenous students acknowledge the importance of their indigenous language and appreciate its role in fostering community identity and connection. They may recognize the benefits of using dominant languages but still prioritize the need for support and resources to ensure their indigenous language thrives. They might also participate in cultural events or language revitalization initiatives.

Among the survey items that measure indigenous language attitude in terms of cognitive aspect, this item ("I am proud to speak my indigenous language, even if some students make fun of it.") obtained the highest mean score of 3.4. This indicates that indigenous students have a strong sense of pride in speaking their indigenous language despite potential ridicule. The survey item with the lowest mean score of 2.8 ("I use dominant languages (Cebuano, Filipino, and English) at school, but I also value and appreciate my indigenous language") still indicates that even though they use the dominant languages, they still value their indigenous language.

Higgins and Maguire (2019) relate in their study that indigenous languages play a crucial role in uniting communities and affirming group identity, embodying cultural heritage, history, and values. Participants McCarty and Nicholas highlight that language mirrors a society's culture, stating, "language holds our culture, our perspective, our history, and our inheritance." This view emphasizes the importance of language in preserving cultural continuity across generations, asserting group identity, and preserving culture.

Furthermore, the preservation of indigenous languages is essential for passing down traditional knowledge and cultural practices (Higgins & Maguire, 2019). Older generations use these indigenous languages to convey their histories and traditions to younger members, strengthening community bonds and ensuring cultural continuity (Joseph, 2024).

Language acts as a vehicle for cultural teachings, which are essential for the health and well-being of indigenous communities (Gonzalez et al., 2017). Thus, the relationship between indigenous languages and dominant languages is complex, with both contributing uniquely to identity, culture, and community resilience. Valuing this chemistry is essential for fostering cultural continuity and strengthening community ties. The findings emphasize that while students are proud of their indigenous language, they also recognize the practical necessity of using dominant languages in educational settings. This duality underscores the need for educational policies that support both the use and revitalization of Indigenous languages alongside dominant languages to promote cultural resilience and community cohesion.

Affective Aspect

The subscale mean score of indigenous language attitude in terms of affective aspect (3.17), the highest among the subscale scores, indicates that indigenous students have a considerable sense of pride and confidence in their language. It suggests that students generally believe that using their indigenous language promotes unity and belonging within their community. They often feel proud and valued when expressing themselves in their indigenous language, showing a significant emotional connection and a positive reception from their peers.

Among the survey items that measure language attitude in terms of affective aspect, this item ("I understand my indigenous language and embrace using it") obtained the highest mean score of 3.6. This indicates that indigenous students have a strong embrace and understanding of their indigenous language among the students. The survey item with the lowest mean score of 2.6 ("I feel more confident expressing myself in my indigenous language than dominant languages") is still indicative that indigenous students value their language, compared to dominant languages.

Cobbo, et al. (2024) indicate in their study that indigenous students feel proud when their indigenous language is used, most especially when it is used at school. Moreover, Highfield, et al., (2024) support that when students use their indigenous language at school, it fosters motivation and a sense of belonging, leading to increased pride in cultural identity among Māori students. Therefore, using indigenous languages in schools boosts motivation, belonging, and pride in cultural heritage.

Behavioral Aspect

The subscale mean score of indigenous language attitude in terms of the behavioral aspect (2.81) is the lowest among the subscale scores, indicating that indigenous students show a moderate level of engagement with their indigenous language. This suggests that students occasionally use their indigenous language in school settings and value its contribution to cultural diversity. While they may choose to speak the dominant language to connect with peers, they still recognize the importance of their indigenous language. Their participation in activities promoting its use is not as consistent, but they do feel a sense of belonging when using both dominant and indigenous languages, indicating a positive attitude toward their cultural heritage.

Among the survey items that measure language attitude in terms of the behavioral aspect, this item ("I am confident speaking my indigenous language, regardless of others' opinions") obtained the highest mean score of 3.5. This indicates that indigenous students have a strong sense of confidence in using their indigenous language in school. The survey item with the lowest mean score of 2.0 ("I use dominant languages (Cebuano, Filipino, and English) at school, but I also recognize the importance and value of my indigenous language") indicates that while students use dominant languages frequently, there is still a notable recognition of the importance of their indigenous language, although with less frequent application in practice.

This result relates to the study in Nigeria, where a significant majority (70.8%) of medical students utilized the Yorùbá language during clinical clerkships despite their education being conducted in English, highlighting a strong inclination to use indigenous languages in practical settings (Olajuyin et al., 2022). However, narratives of indigenous students in Mexico often reveal that they abandon their native languages in favor of Spanish due to acculturation pressures in educational environments ("Narratives of Indigenous University Students in the English Classroom," 2023). The dominance of national languages in education can marginalize indigenous languages, leading to a gradual erosion of cultural identity among students. This tension underscores the need for educational reforms that prioritize indigenous language preservation.

The findings from this subscale indicate that indigenous students display a moderate level of engagement with their language, balancing between the practical use of dominant languages and the cultural significance of their indigenous language. This balance suggests a positive attitude towards their heritage but also highlights the challenges they face in maintaining consistent use of their indigenous language. Educational reforms that promote the active use of indigenous languages, alongside dominant languages, are essential to support cultural continuity and strengthen community ties.

Overall, the scale mean score of indigenous people's attitude score (3.01) means that indigenous students have somewhat positive sentiments towards their indigenous language attitude. They generally feel positive about their language, indicating a supportive environment to some extent. However, there is still room for improvement in promoting stronger positive attitudes and increasing the

visibility and use of the indigenous language within the school. The results of the study reflect the complexities of acculturation among Indigenous students, where positive attitudes towards their language coexist with the challenges posed by the dominant culture. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for creating supportive environments that promote the use and visibility of Indigenous languages within educational settings.

Level of Language Use of Indigenous Students

This discussion investigates the various dimensions of indigenous students' attitudes toward their languages, specifically exploring their connections to these languages, their daily use in various contexts, and their commitment to preserving their linguistic heritage. Through a detailed analysis of survey data, this study examines how these students perceive the significance of their languages in shaping their identities and fostering a sense of unity within their communities. Additionally, it highlights the challenges they face in balancing the use of indigenous languages with the necessity of engaging in dominant languages. By understanding these dynamics, one can better appreciate the importance of indigenous languages in education and the broader societal context, ultimately advocating for initiatives that support language preservation and cultural resilience.

Personal Connection. The subscale mean score of personal connection to indigenous language (3.40), the highest among the subscale scores, indicates that indigenous students have a strong personal connection to their indigenous language. This finding suggests that students firmly believe that using their indigenous language is a fundamental aspect of expressing their cultural identity and who they are as individuals. The use of the indigenous language bonds them closely with their community and connects them significantly to their ancestors.

Among the survey items that measure personal connection to indigenous language, this item ("I cherish the stories I have heard in our language from my family, as they make me feel more like myself") obtained the highest mean score of 3.6. This indicates that students deeply value the cultural stories passed down in their indigenous language. The survey item with the lowest mean score of 3.2 ("I use my indigenous language as a fundamental aspect of expressing my cultural identity.") is still indicative of a positive attitude towards the language's role in cultural identity, highlighting its importance in expressing and maintaining cultural heritage.

This finding aligns with the studies presented by Harry (2021), Charness and Chen (2020), Vicente (2019), and Ghebrekidan (2018), which indicate that Indigenous students have positive attitudes toward their languages, viewing them as vital for their cultural identity. This positive sentiment fosters a sense of pride and belonging within their communities, reinforcing their identity as indigenous individuals. The use of their indigenous language is seen as a way to express who they are and connect with their cultural roots, which is essential for their self-identity and community belonging (Bhatt, 2023; Cruz & Cazorla, 2007). Therefore, using indigenous languages is fundamental for students to express their cultural identity. The interaction of positive attitudes, supportive school culture, and the challenges posed by dominant languages all contribute to this essential aspect of their identity.

Language Use in Daily Life. The subscale mean score of language use in daily life (2.82), the lowest among the subscale scores, indicates that indigenous students do not incorporate the indigenous language into their daily lives. This suggests that students often use the indigenous language in their day-to-day conversations and that family conversations frequently occur in their indigenous language. Additionally, many students express their thoughts and feelings in the indigenous language and actively seek opportunities to incorporate it into various aspects of their lives.

Among the survey items that measure indigenous language use in daily life. This item ("I have conversations within my family mainly in our indigenous language.") obtained the highest mean score of 3.2. This indicates that students have a strong and consistent use of the indigenous language in familiar interactions, believing that families play a critical role in developing and maintaining language habits, which is essential for preserving cultural heritage. The survey item with the lowest mean score of 2.1 ("I seek opportunities to use our indigenous language in my daily activities") reflects students' awareness of the language's importance and their desire to incorporate it into their broader daily lives beyond family settings. Despite the challenges they may face, underscores the value students place on their indigenous language and suggests their commitment to using it in various contexts, including schools and community activities.

Studies support this result, showing that Indigenous students often engage in conversations using their Indigenous languages in their daily lives. This practice reinforces their connection to their cultural identity and heritage, as language is a key component of cultural expression (Deborah, 2023; Gonzalez, 2017). Furthermore, conversations within families frequently occur in indigenous languages. This usage not only strengthens familial bonds but also fosters intergenerational connections, allowing cultural knowledge and traditions to be passed down through language (Olko et al., 2022; Gonzalez et al., 2017; Deborah, 2023). The use of indigenous languages in everyday conversations is crucial for preserving cultural heritage. It allows individuals to express their identity and connect with their roots, which is vital for the continuity of their cultural practices and beliefs (Olko et al., 2022; Gonzalez et al., 2017). Therefore, indigenous languages are frequently used in daily conversations, especially within families. This practice not only reinforces cultural identity but also strengthens community bonds and preserves cultural heritage.

Personal Commitment to Language Preservation. The subscale mean score of personal commitment to language preservation (3.33) indicates that indigenous students have a deep personal commitment to language preservation. It further suggests that students deeply commit themselves to help ensure future generations will use their indigenous language. They always see the importance of helping

keep the indigenous language alive and strongly prioritize speaking the indigenous language even when communicating in multicultural settings.

Among the survey items that measure personal commitment to indigenous language preservation, item ("I consciously choose to use my Indigenous language in everyday conversations to keep it alive") received a mean score of 3.5. This indicates that students' recognition of the importance of daily use of indigenous language is vital to keep it alive. The survey item with the lowest mean score of 2.8 ("I prioritize speaking my Indigenous language even when communicating in multilingual settings") indicates a slightly lower commitment to communicating using indigenous languages in multilingual settings, yet still reflecting an underlying intention to prioritize their indigenous language.

The narrative presented by Harry (2021) supports this result that personal experiences shared by individuals involved in revitalizing the Paiute language illustrate a strong commitment to language preservation. This grassroots movement is critical for keeping languages alive and ensuring they are passed on to future generations. Besides, native language acquisition not only aids in preserving cultural heritage but also enhances cognitive and metalinguistic skills (Wood, 2020). Consequently, students are deeply committed to ensuring the survival of their indigenous languages. They prioritize speaking their language in all settings, recognizing its importance for cultural preservation and community identity. This commitment is essential for keeping their languages alive for future generations.

Community Identity. The subscale mean score of community identity and language (3.36) indicates that indigenous students have a strong sense of community and language. It further suggests that students firmly believe that using indigenous language enhances the sense of unity and belongingness within their community, and helps them show to the world who they are as an indigenous community.

Among the survey items that measure community identity and language, this item ("I sense that the language I speak plays a central role in defining my identity" obtained the highest mean score of 3.5. This indicates a strong recognition among students that their language is crucial to their identity. The survey item with the lowest mean score of 3.2 ("I actively celebrate language diversity within my community") is indicative that Indigenous students value their language, hence, there may be less active engagement in celebrating linguistic diversity within their communities.

Students who learn and speak their indigenous languages gain a deep sense of empowerment and connection. They come to understand that the language they grew up hearing is not just "slang" or "nonsense," but an important aspect of their cultural identity (Aboriginal education | NSW Education Standards. n.d.). Furthermore, the study of Sugue, et al., (2024), involving 96 indigenous college students in the Philippines revealed a strong willingness to communicate in their native languages, highlighting frequent language use and its role in fostering community engagement. The findings suggest that regular use of indigenous languages helps sustain this willingness, promoting a sense of unity among students and their communities. Therefore, students believe that using their indigenous language significantly enhances their sense of unity and belonging within their community. It serves as a vital tool for cultural expression, community cohesion, and pride in their heritage, ultimately helping them showcase their identity to the world.

Overall, the scale mean score of indigenous language score (3.24) indicates that Indigenous students use their indigenous language. It further implies that students have some personal connection to indigenous languages and many times use their indigenous language in daily life. They have some personal commitment to the preservation of their indigenous language and a sense of community identity as indigenous people. United Nations. (2024) mentioned that the use of indigenous languages is linked to preserving invaluable cultural knowledge, which is essential for community cohesion and identity. Hence, Students' strong connection to their indigenous language, evident in their daily use and commitment to its preservation, aligns with Fishbein and Ajzen's Theory of Reasoned Action (1988). Their positive attitude towards the language, stemming from its cultural significance and personal identity, combined with strong social norms within their community, creates a powerful intention to use and protect it. This demonstrates how individual beliefs and social pressures converge to drive behavior, particularly when it comes to cultural practices and identity.

Level of Perception Regarding Their School Culture

This discussion delves into the current state of how schools incorporate Indigenous perspectives, highlighting both successes and areas needing improvement. By examining subscale mean scores related to school culture, curriculum, instruction, and communication patterns, one can gain insights into the efforts made to promote cross-cultural understanding and preserve indigenous languages.

Curriculum. The subscale mean score of school culture in terms of curriculum is (3.17), which means that the school moderately incorporates indigenous languages and cultures into its curriculum. This suggests that students recognize some effort in promoting cross-cultural understanding and preserving Indigenous languages at school. While the school curriculum includes indigenous perspectives and interdisciplinary projects, however, the commitment is not as strong or consistent.

Among the survey items that measure school culture in terms of curriculum, this item ("In our school, the curriculum is culturally responsive in terms of inclusivity of diverse Indigenous languages and dialects") obtained the highest mean score of 3.6. This indicates that Indigenous students have a positive recognition of inclusivity efforts embedded in the curriculum in their school. The survey item with the lowest mean score of 2.7 ("In our school, indigenous language resources, such as textbooks and multimedia materials, are well integrated into the curriculum") indicates that Indigenous students need better integration of indigenous language resources.

In Canada, language revitalization efforts in Indigenous communities are increasingly incorporating adult language courses and

programs, often developed through partnerships between communities and post-secondary institutions (Czaykowska-Higgins, et al., 2017). Education in Canada and the Commonwealth of the Northern Mariana Islands is currently placing greater emphasis on educators embracing the responsibility of incorporating Indigenous perspectives into curricula and teaching practices (Furo, 2018; Misco, 2018). However, the integration of Indigenous perspectives often faces obstacles, such as a lack of representation and the risk of oversimplifying complex cultural narratives, which can lead to stereotypes in education (Developing a critical awareness of Indigenous languages and cultures of Brazil in EFL education, 2023).

Additionally, a key challenge for these initiatives at the post-secondary level is designing programs rooted in Indigenous educational traditions and values while operating within predominantly Euro-Western institutions that have historically contributed to the colonization of Indigenous peoples. Czaykowska-Higgins, et al., (2017). Thus, while efforts to incorporate Indigenous languages and perspectives into curricula are being made across various educational systems, significant challenges remain. The integration of Indigenous knowledge is often inconsistent and faces barriers such as cultural misrepresentation and the complexities of working within institutional frameworks.

Instruction. The subscale mean score of school culture in terms of instruction is 3.17, indicating that teachers moderately integrate and support Indigenous languages in their instructions. This suggests that students see some effort from their teachers to include indigenous language elements and support their learning. Teachers recognize the importance of indigenous languages, but the integration and encouragement are less consistent.

Among the survey items that measure school culture in terms of instruction, this item ("In our school, teachers value the cultural significance of Indigenous languages") obtained the highest mean score of 3.5. This indicates that indigenous students feel that their teachers appreciate the cultural importance of the indigenous languages. The survey item with the lowest mean score of 2.9 ("In our school, teachers in my class encourage me to ask questions about indigenous languages") indicates that indigenous students have less encouragement from their teachers to engage actively with the use of indigenous languages in classroom discussions.

In New Zealand, many language teachers advocate for the inclusion of indigenous knowledge, such as te reo Māori, in their curricula, acknowledging its significance in promoting cultural competence (Wang, 2023). However, many teachers feel apprehensive about using indigenous languages, especially in technical subjects like math and science. This apprehension can limit the extent to which they integrate these languages into their teaching practices. Although teachers do not regularly reference or use home languages in their daily practices, they generally express a willingness to explore incorporating activities that involve these languages (Bailey & Marsden, 2017). Therefore, while teachers moderately integrate and support indigenous languages in their instruction, various factors such as societal attitudes, policy support, and community involvement play a significant role in shaping this integration.

Patterns of Communication. The subscale mean score of school culture in terms of patterns of communication is 3.18. This means that the school makes a moderate effort to include indigenous languages in its communication patterns. It suggests that students see some representation and celebration of Indigenous languages in activities and events. There is occasional support for students to share their languages and participate in language revitalization projects. While the environment is generally inclusive, the efforts to promote and support indigenous languages are less consistent.

Among the survey items that measure school culture in terms of pattern of Communication, this item ("In our school, there are opportunities for students to showcase their proficiency in their Indigenous language through literature and music") obtained the highest mean score of 3.5. Indicates that indigenous students have a positive recognition of opportunities provided for showcasing language proficiency. The survey item with the lowest mean score of 2.5 ("In our school, Indigenous languages are underrepresented in activities and events") indicates that indigenous students experience a lack of representation of indigenous languages in school activities and events.

Indigenous language schools in the U.S. prioritize community involvement, employing technology and traditional storytelling to engage students and help preserve their languages (Kusumaningsih, 2022). Moreover, a school environment that values linguistic diversity can positively influence students' attitudes towards their indigenous languages. When students see their languages represented in school events, it can contribute to a supportive atmosphere that encourages them to use their languages more frequently (Bhatt, 2023; Winner 2022; Cruz & Cazorla, 2007). The use of Indigenous communication arts, such as folk songs and drama, can enhance cultural identity and promote social change, suggesting a pathway for schools to celebrate Indigenous languages (Issahaku et al., 2024). Furthermore, research indicates that the use of indigenous language at school not only fosters cultural pride but also enhances the transmission of cultural knowledge to younger generations (Banay, 2024).

So, fostering a school culture that includes Indigenous languages in communication patterns and activities can positively impact students' connection to their linguistic heritage. By incorporating community involvement, technology, and traditional arts like storytelling and folk songs, schools can create a more inclusive environment that not only preserves Indigenous languages but also strengthens cultural identity and promotes social change.

Overall, the scale mean score of School Culture (3.17), means that indigenous students have somewhat positive sentiments towards school culture which can be connected to Acculturation Theory and the Theory of Reasoned Action. This theory emphasizes the significance of a supportive environment in shaping cultural identities and influencing behaviors. By fostering greater engagement with

indigenous communities, integrating Indigenous languages and traditions into the curriculum, and promoting respect for cultural diversity, schools can strengthen students' sense of belonging and well-being. This, in turn, can enhance their intentions and behaviors toward using Indigenous languages, contributing to their preservation and revitalization.

Indigenous students might feel generally positive, though there could still be room for improvement. This indicates that while the school environment is supportive and inclusive to an extent, further efforts could enhance this positivity and ensure a healthier sense of belonging and respect for cultural diversity.

Moderation Estimates of School Culture on the Causal Relationship Between Indigenous People's Language Attitude and Language Usage

This study discusses the relationship between indigenous people's attitudes toward language use and the role of school culture in fostering indigenous language retention and use. Findings suggest that the effectiveness of incorporating indigenous languages into educational settings may vary based on the level of commitment and cultural responsiveness of the school. Moderate efforts by schools appear to enhance indigenous language use, though at high levels of school integration, this effect may diminish.

Results show that there is a significant causal relationship between indigenous people's attitudes on indigenous language use at low and average levels of school culture with p-values of 0.004 and 0.001 respectively. However, such a causal relationship becomes insignificant at a high level of school culture with a p-value of 0.397. This indicates that indigenous people's attitude has a significant effect on indigenous language use when the school would exert effort, from a limited to moderate level, to incorporate indigenous language and culture into its curriculum, instruction, and pattern of communication. At a high level of the school's effort of incorporation, the causal relationship between the two variables becomes insignificant. This result suggests that improving school culture alone may not be sufficient; educators and policymakers should also focus on integrating curricula that emphasize indigenous languages, training teachers in culturally responsive methods, and engaging families and communities in supporting language use.

This connection is further supported by various studies highlighting the importance of culturally responsive education and immersion programs. Culturally responsive education enhances academic achievement for Indigenous populations (Siekman et al., 2017) and incorporating Indigenous languages into the curriculum leads to better retention and learning outcomes (Grover, 2017).

Case studies, such as those from the Native American Community Academy, demonstrate successful language reclamation efforts (McCarty & Lee, 2015), while comparative studies show that decentralized decision-making in education supports indigenous language instruction (Ward & Braudt, 2015). Despite the clear benefits of integrating indigenous languages in education, challenges remain, including the need for appropriate teaching materials and overcoming historical assimilationist policies that have marginalized these languages. Addressing these challenges is essential for fostering a more inclusive educational environment.

Combining community involvement with solid school programs is likely the best approach for revitalizing indigenous languages. Indigenous people's attitudes significantly influence the use of Indigenous languages, especially in educational settings where schools incorporate Indigenous culture and language into their curricula (Darbonne, et al., 2023).

A systematic review highlights that integrating Indigenous knowledge into primary education fosters cultural preservation and community empowerment, emphasizing the role of teachers and community members in developing educational materials to enhance family participation and strengthen school-community connections (da Silva et al., 2023).

However, a study on Australian Indigenous education reveals a disconnect between policies prioritizing language and cultural education and actual practices, contributing to the decline of Indigenous languages. This suggests that without effective community engagement and culturally relevant teaching methods, school efforts can be less impactful (Lees & Bang, 2023). The study advocates for immersive bilingual programs where children learn in their native languages before transitioning to national languages, promoting better educational outcomes (Nakata, 2023).

These findings further suggest that while moderate school efforts positively affect language use, poorly implemented initiatives may weaken the relationship between Indigenous attitudes and language preservation, highlighting the need for thoughtful integration of cultural elements into education. Hence, collaborative efforts such as that in Montana, particularly the Séliš language program, demonstrated increased student interest in Indigenous culture and language proficiency through thoughtful partnerships (Brayko, et al., 2022). Similarly, strategies in Canada emphasize the importance of digital technologies for making language resources accessible, which can revitalize endangered languages (Wang, 2024).

Conclusions

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